

1 **TLE gene expression is dysregulated in inflammatory bowel disease.**

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6 Through integration of whole transcriptome data from cells of the immune system and from cultured cells
7 that model NOD2 transcriptional function, and from study of intestinal biopsy tissues from healthy humans
8 and patients with disease, we discovered profound dysregulation of TLE gene expression control in
9 patients with Crohn's Disease and by the major Crohn's Disease susceptibility gene, NOD2. TLE
10 expression control by human NOD2 and the gram negative pathogen associated molecular pattern
11 muramyl dipeptide was complex. The TLE4 gene lied under the control of wild-type human NOD2 in a
12 heterologous system, but TLE4 expression was activated in NOD2 mutant monocytes from patients with
13 Crohn's Disease. TLE1 was modestly repressed by wild-type human NOD2; repression of TLE1 in a
14 heterologous HEK293 system was significantly enhanced upon expression of Crohn's Disease NOD2
15 leucine-rich region mutant L1007P. TLE4 differential expression at the transcriptome-level could be
16 observed in the terminal ileum of patients with Crohn's Disease. We isolated genomic sequences of TLE2
17 as among the most differentially methylated following lipopolysaccharide stimulation of macrophages by
18 applying genomic technologies to studying changes in DNA methylation in association with pattern
19 recognition in immune cells. In macrophages from patients with Blau Syndrome which contain the R334W
20 mutation in the centrally located nucleotide-bonding domain (NBD) of NOD2, TLE4 expression was
21 repressed. Utilizing transcriptomic methods to discover TLE co-regulated gene partners revealed TLE4
22 was transcriptionally co-regulated with NCOA3, TET2, Sp100, PHF11, NR3C1 and the major IBD
23 susceptibility gene TRIM22, whose mutation is thought to associate with fistulizing (penetrating) perianal
24 Crohn's Disease in a monogenic fashion. Systems biological examination indicated TLE family control of
25 Wnt ligands 4 and 6 and TCF/LEF factors Tcf711 and Tcf712. Monocytes from patients with Crohn's
26 Disease failed to express Tcf711 and Tcf712, and in response to muramyl dipeptide, were defective in
27 Wnt5b production. Control of TLE gene expression by wild-type and human NOD2 is extraordinarily
28 complex but continued unbiased systems biological methodologies can deconvolute difficult to understand
gene expression changes in human disease.

1 **Results**

2 **I. TLE4 expression is activated in the terminal ileum of humans with Crohn's Disease.**

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4 GSE20881

5 *n*=6 terminal ileum (control; healthy)
6 *n*=17 terminal ileum (Crohn's Disease)

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ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
30590	5.19e-05	-4.9154619	1.96722	-0.26768824	TLE4	63/39140	99.8
11660	4.11e-03	-3.173076	-1.93759	-0.27879902	TLE1	1278/39140	96.7

19 GSE193667

20 *n*=120 ileum; control (healthy)
n=132 ileum; patients with Crohn's Disease (non-active disease, non-inflamed)

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GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
7088	1.00e-03	0.0741	-3.2891647	-0.2435814	383.88	TLE1	2396/23072	89.6
7091	1.10e-02	0.0547	-2.5421895	-0.1390614	575.99	TLE4	7129/23072	69.1

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II. Control of TLE gene family expression by NOD2.

a. In a heterologous system (wild-type human NOD2 expressed in HEK293 embryonic kidney cells):

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n=3 HEK293T; empty vector (mock transduced)

n=3 wild-type human NOD2 HEK293T (stably transduced)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
235765_at	6.84e-02	-2.2628725	-4.293194	-0.630459	TLE4	6006/54675	89.0
233575_s_at	1.21e-01	-1.8317856	-4.852436	-0.6143841	TLE4	9792/54675	82.1
228284_at	1.38e-01	1.73596	-4.974273	0.3039371	TLE1	10875/54675	80.1
212769_at	1.53e-01	-1.660463	-5.069069	-0.4704659	TLE3	11841/54675	78.3
203221_at	1.93e-01	1.4821999	-5.287359	0.2723181	TLE1	14314/54675	73.8
206472_s_at	2.21e-01	-1.3797853	-5.408282	-0.5190613	TLE3	15977/54675	70.8
40837_at	2.37e-01	1.3273904	-5.468604	0.2997715	TLE2	16871/54675	69.1
1553813_s_at	3.77e-01	-0.960646	-5.852618	-0.3526765	TLE6	24744/54675	54.7

b. In a heterologous system (human NOD2 L1007fsinsC expressed in HEK293 human cells):

GSE22611

n=3 HEK293T; empty vector (mock transduced)

n=3 L1007fsinsC human NOD2 HEK293T (stably transduced)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
227130_s_at	2.76e-02	2.9725245	-3.153697	0.93869376	TLE1	1732/54675	96.8
233575_s_at	7.43e-02	-2.1983661	-4.062405	-0.55113836	TLE4	4328/54675	92.1
228340_at	2.54e-01	-1.2732933	-5.141817	-0.22169275	TLE3	14354/54675	73.7
1553813_s_at	3.33e-01	-1.0613402	-5.355315	-0.42913157	TLE6	18691/54675	65.8
204431_at	8.95e-01	0.1379512	-5.903127	0.0447913	TLE2	48963/54675	10.4

c. In monocytes humans with Crohn's Disease, containing CD-associated NOD2 variants (both homozygous SNP "8" and heterozygous SNPs "12" and "13"):

GSE69446

n=2 monocytes; healthy

n=3 monocytes; humans with CD (NOD2 mutant; *n*=1 SNP8 and *n*=2 SNP12/13)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
166	2.63e-03	0.165	3.00829	0.4954819	3463.03	TLE5	677/17330	96.1
7088	1.40e-01	0.324	1.475823	0.4775716	137.49	TLE1	3612/17330	79.2
7091	2.54e-01	0.255	1.141646	0.2910803	2335.65	TLE4	5331/17330	69.2
7090	7.20e-01	0.208	-0.358655	-0.0747533	3635.57	TLE3	12009/17330	30.7

d. In iPS-derived macrophages from patients with Blau syndrome containing a mutation in the nucleotide-binding domain (NOD2 R334W), as compared to wild-type, control ESC-derived macrophages.

GSE98454

n=2 macrophages (human; wild-type and wild-type [corrected])

n=1 macrophages (human; Blau Syndrome; R334W)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
7091	7.27e-01	0.306	3.49e-01	0.10676354	1058.99	TLE4	6086/15635	61.1
7090	1.82e-01	0.252	1.34	0.33643274	2764.61	TLE3	9346/15635	40.2
166	8.64e-01	0.268	1.71e-01	0.0458795	3509.56	TLE5	11277/15635	27.9
7089	8.62e-01	0.708	1.73e-01	0.12275667	128.02	TLE2	11276/15635	32.2
79816	8.88e-01	1.924	-1.41e-01	-0.27214056	13.72	TLE6	15274/15635	2.0

III. Among the most differentially methylated regions (DMRs) in the human macrophage genome lipopolysaccharide stimulation is a position residing with the TLE2 gene.

IV. TLE4 is transcriptionally co-regulated with a network of nuclear factors and the major IBD susceptibility gene *TRIM22*.

Query genes:

Query Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value	Description
TLE4	7091	-3.2000	0.0033	transducin-like enhancer of split 4 (E(sp1) homolog, Drosophila)

Coexpressed genes:

Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value	Rank	%Co-reg
TRIM22	10346	1.1669	0.0064	23	99.9

Out of 17795 total transcripts

V. The TLE family functions in concert with WNT factors WNT4 and WNT6 and the transcription factors TCF7L1 and TCF7L2.

We also found a network of nuclear factors that the TLE family was co-regulated with in human tissues, including KDM6B, KDM4B, HDAC5, BRD1, and BRD3.

Query genes:

Query Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value	Rank	%Co-reg
TLE1	7088	0.2565	0.0004		
TLE2	7089	0.4889	0.0001		
TLE4	7091	-0.0343	0.3158		
TLE3	7090	0.0366	0.3191		
TLE6	79816	0.3018	0.0018		
WNT4	54361	0.1777	0.0443	1387/17784	92.2
WNT6	7475	0.1786	0.1265	1377/17784	92.3
TCF7L1	83439	0.2798	0.0057	208/17784	98.8
TCF7L2	6934	0.2623	0.0032	315/17784	98.2

1 **VI. Monocytes from humans with Crohn's Disease are defective in production of Wnt5b in**
2 **response to muramyl dipeptide.**

3 GSE69446

4 *n*=2 monocytes; healthy +MDP

5 *n*=3 monocytes; humans with CD (NOD2 mutant; *n*=1 SNP8 and *n*=2 SNP12/13) +MDP

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
81029	6.52e-04	0.401	3.4088077	1.3666513	247.08	WNT5B	184/16911	98.9

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8 **VII. NOD2 L1007PinsC expression in a heterologous system recapitulates failure to activate**
9 **Wnt5b in Crohn's Disease.**

10 GSE22611

11 *n*=3 HEK293T; empty vector (mock transduced)

12 *n*=3 L1007fsinsC human NOD2 HEK293T (stably transduced)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
221029_s_at	1.36E-01	1.7479203	-4.604443	2.04567878	WNT5B	7740/54675	85.8

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15 **VIII. Monocytes from humans with Crohn's Disease are defective in Tcf7l2 and Tcf7l2 expression.**

16 GSE69446

17 *n*=2 monocytes; healthy

18 *n*=3 monocytes; humans with CD (NOD2 mutant; *n*=1 SNP8 and *n*=2 SNP12/13)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
6934	5.87e-05	0.469	-4.017846	-1.8825869	493.77	TCF7L2	249/17330	98.6
83439	8.03e-02	0.701	-1.74906	-1.2262858	21.59	TCF7L1	2677/17330	84.6

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22 **Discussion**

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24 We demonstrate here using systems biological methods that the TLE gene family is dysregulated
25 in the inflammatory bowel disease Crohn's Disease, that this is a direct consequence of expression of the
26 Crohn's Disease NOD2 pattern recognition receptor mutant L1007fsinsC, that the TLE gene family
27 controls expression of Wnt ligands and Tcf7l1/Tcf7l2, and that expression of Wnt ligands and Tcf7l1/l2 is
28 defective in the cells of humans with Crohn's Disease.

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References

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